

Constructing an Appropriate Aircraft's Liability of Passengers

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Abstract

The method used in this research is the method of normative legal research with the type of data in the form of primary legal materials consist of the Warsaw Convention of 1929, Law No. 15 of 1992 on Aviation. Act No. 1 of 2009 on Aviation, Government Regulation No. 40 of 1995, the Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 on Liability Carrier Air Transport. Secondary law material in this study in the form of expert opinions aviation law, whereas non-legal material is in the form of Indonesian Dictionary, Dictionary of Aviation. Legal materials collection techniques done by literature search. Results of this study found that the terms of the start of the air carrier liability in respect of damage suffered by passengers are starting to an agreement between the air transport with the passenger aircraft with a printed ticket that contains the names of passengers, departure airport, destination airport, flight times, fares paid by passengers.

Keywords: aircraft's liability, passengers

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Since the enactment of the Warsaw Convention of 1929 and several other international protocols, especially with regard to the requirements of an airline provide compensation if passengers from the airline accidents causing harm to passengers.

Through several aircraft accidents that occurred in Indonesia include Garuda Indonesia plane crash on Mount Burangrang Bandung in 1961, Merpati air dated 10 October 1971 in Makassar, on 29 March 1977 in Tinombala, Garuda airlines on 11 July 1979 in Polonia, Merpati air in 1985 in London, Garuda airlines on April 4th, 1987 in Polonia, Merpati air dated May 23, 1987 in Ruteng NTT, Garuda airlines on 26 September 1997 in articles for North Sumatra, Silk Air December 19, 1997 in Palembang, Garuda airlines dated January 16, 2002 in Solo, Lion Air on 30 november 2004 at Airport Adisumarmo Solo, Mandala air September 5, 2005 in Polonia, Adam Air January 1, 2007 in western Sulawesi and Garuda airlines on 7 March 2007 in the AdiSuctpto Airport, Yogyakarta.

From all aircraft accident that claimed the lives of the foregoing, the air transport providing compensation to the victims or their heirs without waiting for a lawsuit in state court. Provision of compensation to victims of aircraft accidents after research the cause of the aircraft accident, whether already meets the requirements or not. The requirement is meant here is, as referred to in Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention of 1929, are (1) the loss must be caused by an accident; (2) The accident should be have something to do with air transport; (3) The accident should be occur in an aircraft, or during passenger embarkation and disembarkation activities. These requirements are coercive provisions (*dwingend recht*), means if these requirements are not fulfilled, transport can not be requested the liability lawsuit.

Requirement that was contained in Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention in 1929 was intended to provide protection to airlines because at that time no entrepreneurs who want to invest in the field of air transport due to the capital-intensive businesses and highly risky. Along with the advances in technology and business fields, including the field of insurance business, the requirements contained in Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention 1929 has been very inadequate development.

1.2 Problems

- a. Identification of equitable compensation;
- b. Formulation of the scope and timing;
- c. How to institute this concept that adhered to by all parties?

1.3 Research Methods

The method used in this research is the method of normative legal research and the type of data in the form of primary legal materials consist of the Warsaw Convention of 1929, Law No. 15 of 1992 on Flights, Law No. 1 of 2009 on Flight, Government Regulation No. 40 of 1995, Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 on Liability Carrier Air Transport. Secondary law material in this study in the form of expert opinions aviation law, whereas non-legal material is in the form of Indonesian Dictionary, Dictionary of Aviation. Data collection technique of legal materials was done by doing a search of the literature.

2. Research Result

During this time, the requirements of airlines provide compensation to passengers who suffered losses as a result of the accident were (1) The airplane accident, (2) There is a relation with the air carrier, (3) embarkation and disembarkation.

The provisions which regulate the terms of the air carrier Liability is not clearly stated in Law No. 1 of 2009 on Aviation. To get clarity on the terms of the Liability air carrier, found in the 1929 Warsaw Convention which is contained in Article 17 which states that the carrier is Liability for damages arising must meet the requirements that the losses caused by an accident; accident would be within the aircraft (on board the aircraft); The accident should occur at the time of embarkation or disembarkation (in the course of any of the operations of embarking or disembarking).

2.1 Definition of “Accident”

Restrictions or understanding of accidents; in international air transport, an “accident” is the first condition to the implementation of the provisions of the Convention and is the obligation of the plaintiff to assert the existence of “accident”. In 1929 Warsaw Convention clearly was not found the formulation of the expressions of the interpretation must be sought from the opinion of scholars or of a court decision.

In search of cases of aircraft accidents internationally conclusion that in order for an incident to qualify as an “accident” within the meaning of Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention, the incidence of the aircraft that caused the damages should be an event that exceptional (unusual) or unpredictable (unexpected).

Furthermore, if the incident or accident was the result of a physical state of the passenger or defect of goods or a state that has nothing to do with air transport, it is not an accident as intended by Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention. It is logical if the carrier cannot be responsible for any loss or injury caused by the physical state or the health of passengers or defect of the item itself, because it has nothing to do with air transport.

Dictionary of Legal and Regulatory Flight, accident (accident) is an event that occurs outside the human allegations relating to aircraft operations that took place since the passengers boarding with

the intention of taking flight to the destination until all the passengers get off (disembarkation) of the aircraft at the destination airport. These events led to the death or serious injuries, minor injuries, injuries that resulted in permanent or temporary (a) collision with the aircraft, or (b) direct contact with parts of the airplane or (c) exposed direct blows of jet engine aircraft, or (d) aircraft require major repairs or (e) requires the replacement of components on aircraft or (f) aircraft completely lost.

Indonesia so far in the interpretation of the notion of accident (accident) mentioned in Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention or Article 24 Air Freight Ordinance (OPU) in 1939 has never been questioned, since every aircraft accident occurs, the settlement of the losses is determined based on changing government policies are always accepted by both parties.

2.2 Definition “There is a Correlation with Air Freight”

As a second condition stipulated in Article 24 of the Air Transport Ordinance to determine the scope of carrier liability is if the accident has a connection with air transport. If an accident that causes damage to the passenger has nothing to do with the airlift, then the air carrier shall not be liability lawsuit.

Thus, the scope of the domestic air carrier liability, which refers to the provisions of Ordinance Air Freight narrower than the scope of liability for International air carrier that uses the Warsaw Convention 1929. In Warsaw Convention of 1929, despite the losses suffered by the passengers it has nothing to do with air transport, as long as the result of an accident and occurred in the airplane or at the time did embarkation and disembarkation, the carrier should be liability.

For example, suppose a passenger suffered injuries due to being stabbed by another passenger next to him without the knowledge of the carrier or his crew, then according to the Warsaw Convention carrier remains liability, while according to the 1939 Ordinance Air Freight carrier is not liability. Another example, a passenger died in an airplane without an accident, according to the Warsaw Convention 1929, the carrier should be liable, the case of Munir's death in an aircraft Garuda Indonesia flight from Jakarta to Amsterdam route with a transit in Changi Singapore, can be used as a case study. Meanwhile, according to Ordinance 1939 Air Freight carrier no liability; take the example case of the death of Dr. Ridawan, lecturer of the Faculty of Animal Husbandry Universitas Mataram Garuda Indonesia in Mataram-Jakarta route.

2.3 Definition of “In Aircraft”

Definition of the aircraft; as well as accident, there is no sense what the meant of in aircraft by the Warsaw Convention 1929. At first glance it seems the phrase 'in an aircraft' provide clear boundaries when the carrier should be liability; but in practice it turns out not so. When an aircraft experiencing an emergency landing, the passengers asked to get off and wait around the plane then crashed, whether the accident occurred can be interpreted in an aircraft referred to the Warsaw Convention?

According to some legal experts in Indonesia, including Saefullah Wiradipradja, said that in terms of the juridical sense 'in an aircraft' (on board the aircraft) does not mean solely if passengers are physically located in the fuselage, but also including where passengers were (physical) outside the aircraft caused by abnormal circumstances; means the existence of the passengers outside the aircraft is not due to the expiration of a trip as defined under air transport agreements. So that if a passenger suffers a loss or accident during outside air caused by the abnormal condition of the carrier still must be accountable. Of course, the carrier may be exempted from liability if the loss or injury was caused by the passenger's own fault or because of health condition.

2.4 Definition of “Embarkation and Disembarkation”

Definition of embarkation and disembarkation; the Warsaw Convention does not provide a definition of what is meant by heading to the plane or leaving the plane (in the course of the operations of embarking or disembarking). Consequently, there are differences of interpretation, particularly since when the process begins embarkation and disembarkation until when the process ends.

Is clear and is not a problem when an accident suffered by a passenger when he rose to or dropped from an aircraft shall be deemed to occur at the time of embarkation or disembarkation. But in practice issues arise in the event of an accident or loss occurs when the passenger was in the waiting room airports before boarding the plane and at a time waiting for luggage after descending from the aircraft. The question is, whether these circumstances were included or not included in the scope of Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention?

There are several opinions about the meaning of embarkation (leading to the aircraft) and disembarkation (leaving the aircraft):

- a. The first opinion, which is led by D. Lureau, stating that started since passenger embarkation leave the building airports in order toward the runway, and ends at the time of disembarkation of passengers entering the building at the destination airport.
- b. The second opinion, which was initiated by the Matte and Kahn-Freund, stating that the period of time starting from the passenger embarkation under the supervision of employees of the airline (carrier) in order to get to the aircraft, and ended at the time the employee leaves after dropping off their passengers entered the building at the destination airport.
- c. The third opinion, from a court in the United States, stating that the embarkation process initiated since the 'check in' and the process ends after disembarkation of passengers take the trunk (registered luggage). This opinion is supported by the presence of a court decision in the United States stating that the carrier is accountable to passengers who had an accident on the escalator when heading baggage claim. The Court of Appeal in Berlin in a case stating that the transporter accountable for accidents of passengers in the airport building after the 'check in' to the plane, because the obligation to supervise the transport of passengers and goods were started since passenger do 'check in'.

This opinion is very broad and difficult to materialize, because the check-in counter at each airport consists of many transporters and are still in place that can be passed by a lot of people so it is very difficult to distinguish passenger carrier with each other. In addition, to provide optimum service, air freight carrier now provides service check in via the internet, or also using city facilities check in who made no later than one day before the scheduled departure, while service users are not in the airport.

According to the authors, the determination of embarkation began users of air transport services (passengers) do boarding and disembarkation ends when the passenger enters the arrival gate. According to the author, is the embarkation and disembarkation of passengers during the activities that have been set by transporters (based on the instructions and under the transporters control) well before the 'ride to' or after 'down from' aircraft, the transporters should be liable.

The terms mentioned Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention in 1929 was intended to provide protection to the airlines, because it is the beginning of the aviation industry which requires a lot of capital and the risk is enormous. While today, in line with the growth of the business, including insurance companies, then the conditions contained in Article 17 of the Warsaw Convention 1929 has been extremely inadequate, including the protection of passengers.

Application requirements provision of compensation to passengers who suffered losses as a result of the accident so far only focused on the aircraft accident, but one thing is forgotten since when the legal relationship between the airline (air transport) with a passenger?

Legal relationship that occurs between the transporter by passenger aircraft is a crucial moment the position of both parties. It is said that, because the legal relationship between transporter by passengeran agreement the start of an air transport agreement. Agreement is the most important source of lead

Law of obligations, the most widely obligations published by an agreement when compared to other sources, namely legislation. The obligations that was born of the agreement was desired by two people or parties who make an agreement, while Law of obligations born of the law held by law

outside the will of the parties concerned. If two people entered into an agreement, then they mean is that between them it applies Law of obligations.

Agreements transport of an agreement between the first party called the transport air by the second party, called the transport services, where the first party is obliged to transport from and to and from the destination of passengers and / or goods securely and safely, while the second party is obliged to pay the fare transport.

Examine the definition of the transport agreement, as mentioned above, it can be said that the carrier is obliged to transport the freight to and from your destination safe and sound, while the right transporter is receiving transport costs. The fundamental question is, since when the agreement started?

Legal relationship between transporter the passenger is from the lack of agreement between the two which led to the rights and obligations, namely with a printed ticket that contains the passenger name, flight route, flight time (day, date, month, year, time) and ticket prices. The agreement between the transporter and the passenger plane was an agreement between them to be obeyed because it is legislation for both.

With the printed ticket, then all rights and obligations between the parties with the passenger air transport has been in effect, meaning that in the event of losses suffered by the passengers after the printing of the ticket are the responsibility of the carrier to compensate the losses suffered by the passengers. This indeed is a very heavy responsibility for air transport, but that does not mean this responsibility should be avoided, but that responsibility must be faced. Given how heavy the burden borne by the air transport, the risk of liability for damages is transferred to another party the insurer. Thus, the burden of responsibility that should be borne by the air transport is transferred to the insurer, the premium of the insurance liability charged to the passenger who had been attached to the ticket prices.

Compensation for losses suffered by passengers who have had air ticket from the printed ticket is a manifestation of the agreement on air transport agreement between the air carrier with the transport service users is a moment that is very fair for both sides. Say so, because the passenger has paid the cost of transportation from the printed ticket by the carrier, wherein the component has been attached ticket the liability insurance premium payments. It is natural that the responsibility of carrier starting printed ticket, because since the agreement between carrier and the passenger has begun.

The responsibility of the air carrier began printed tickets that have been agreed upon by the passenger is a new concept in the world of aviation, it should be arrangements in place for implementation in the legislation in order to force the airlines for the air carrier to comply.

3. Conclusion

From the description above, it can be drawn some conclusions, as follows:

- a. That the condition of the air carrier liability were applied during the existence of the accident; the accident occurred in the airplane or nothing to do with the aircraft; and occurs between the embarkation and disembarkation is no longer sufficient if it is associated with the business progress of aviation technology and air transport;
- b. That the results of research that has been done, the air carrier liability to passengers starting from the signing of the agreement between the air carrier with the passengers marked with printed air ticket containing the passenger's name, flight number, flight time, the airport of origin and destination airports, departure time and estimated arrival time at the airport destination.
- c. For more effective implementation of the requirements of this air carrier liability, it should be placed in the state legislation.

References

- [1] Abdurrasyid, Priyatna, 1979, *State sovereignty in the Air Space*, Space Law Research Center, Jakarta.
- [2] -----, 1980, *Some Fundamentals of the National Air Transportation Legal Developments*, Binacipta, Jakarta.
- [3] Al-Ifriqi al-misri, IbnuManzur, 1994, *Lisanu Al Arabi*, Daru al Fikri, Beirut.
- [4] Badruzaman, Mariam Darus, 1986, *Judging from the Consumer Protection against Angle Baku Treaty (Standard), Symposium on Legal Aspects of Consumer Protection*, Binacipta, Jakarta.
- [5] Bentham, Jeremy, 2006, *Legislation Invitation theory, Principles of Legislation, Civil Law and Criminal Law*, Nuansa, Bandung.
- [6] Black MA, Henry Campbell, 1968, *Black's Law Dictionary, Revised Fourth Edition*, Minn West Publishing, Co, ST Paul.
- [7] Boyle, Fiona, et.al, 2003, *A Practical Guide to Lawyering Skills*, Cavendish Publishing Limited, London.
- [8] Djojodihardjo, Moegni, 1979, *Act against the law*, PradnyaParamita, Jakarta.
- [9] Diederiks-Verschuur, I.P.H., 1985, *An Introduction to Air Law*, Deventer: Kluwer.
- [10] -----, Diederiks-Verschuur, *Sumilarities With and Differences Between Air and Space Law*, Martinus Publisher, 1991.
- [11] Dobbs, Dan.B, 1988, *Torts and Compensation, Personal Accountability and Socia Responsibility for Injury, American Casebook Series*, West Publishing company.
- [12] Drion, H, 1975, *Limitation of Liabilities in International Air Law*, The Hague :MartinusNijhoff.
- [13] Emson, Raymond, 1999, *Evidence*, New York: MacMillan.
- [14] Fleming, J.G, 1977, *the Law of Torts*, the Law Book Company, Sydney;
- [15] Fridman, J.G, 1978, *Introduction to the Law of Torts*, London:Butterworths.
- [16] Gill, Mc, 1991, *Annals of Air and Space Law*, Annales de DraoitAerienet Spatial.
- [17] Glaser Barney, 1984, *The Discovey of Grounded Theory*, Aldine Publishing Company, Chicago.
- [18] Hutchinson, Terry, 2002, *Researching and Writing in Law*, Lawbook Co, Queensland University of Technology.
- [19] Kantaatmadja, MiekeKomar, 1984, *Various Issues Air and Space Law*, RemadjaKarya, Bandung.
- [20] Lebacqz, Karen, 1986, *Theory of Justice, Six Theories of Justice*, Nusa Media, Bandung.
- [21] Magdelenat, Jean-Louis, 1981, *Air Cargo, Regilation and Claims*, London:Butterworths.
- [22] Mankiewicz, 1981, *the Liability Regime, of the International Air Carriage*, Deventer: Kluwer.
- [23] Miller, Georgette, 1977, *Liability in International Air Transport*, Deventer: Kluwer.
- [24] Nozick, Robert, 1974, *Anarchy, Statem and Utopia*, New York :BasicBokks,
- [25] Prent, K, et.al, 1969, *Latin Indonesian dictionary*, Kanisius, Yaogyakarta.
- [26] Prodjudikoro, Wirjono, 1973, *the principles of the Law of Treaties, 2nd ed*, Vorking, Bandung.
- [27] -----, 2000, *Unlawful acts Light of Civil Law*, MandarMadju, Bandung.
- [28] Rawls, John, 1995, *a Theory of Justice*, PustakaPelajar, Yogyakarta.
- [29] Redfern, Alan and Martin Hunter, 1999, *Law and Practice of International Commercial Arbitration*, Sweet&Maxwell, London.
- [30] Sumobaskoro, Suhono, 1975, *the New Aprproach to the Indonesian Air TransportPolicy: Its Stratgec Economic Factors and Pittals*, Universitas Indonesia Library, Jakarta.
- [31] Verschuur, Diederiks, 1985, *an Introduction to Air Law*, Kluwer Law and Taxation Publishers, Deventer, Netherlands.
- [32] Wade, HWR and C.F. Forsyth, 1994, *Administrative Law*, Oxford University Press, 7 ed, New York.
- [33] Wassenbergh, Henri, 1993, *Principles and Practices in Air Transport Regulation*, ITA Les Preses, Paris, France.

- [34] -----, 1992, *Air and Space Law de Lege Ferende*, MartinusNijhoff Publishers, Boston, London.
- [35] Wasenbergh, H.A, and H.P. van Fenema (ed) 1981, *International Air Transport in the Eighties*, Deventer: Kluwer.
- [36] Williams, Glanville and B.A. Hepple, 1976, *Foundations of the Law of Tort*, London:Butterworths.
- [37] Wiradipradja, Syaefullah, 1989, *Responsibility of Carrier in the International Air Transport Law and the National*, Liberty, Yogyakarta;
- [38] Zhang, Yong 1999, *Comparative Studies on Governmental Liability in East and Southeast Asia*, Kluwer Law International, London.